

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Kōji Igarashi

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Good day, dear readers. Today, I will talk about another important Japanese creative in the world of video games: Mr. Kōji Igarashi, also known as “IGA.”

Nowadays, Igarashi is internationally recognized in the electronic entertainment industry for having given the *Castlevania* video game series the distinctive characteristics that make it most recognizable to the franchise’s most devoted vampire-hunting enthusiasts. Not without reason, the games in the series in which he participates are often called “Igarashia.”

However, in this article, I will talk not only about his involvement with the saga of the Belmonts, Dracula, and company, but also about other projects in which this creative has worked.

Igarashi’s Early Days in Video Games

Castlevania was already a series that Igarashi enjoyed as a player long before he started working at the well-known Japanese developer and publisher Konami. However, it would take several years after joining the company before he would actually participate in these games.

After finishing high school, Kōji considered working in the video game industry while continuing his studies at university. He tried to join another company before trying his luck at Konami, but a disagreement with that company’s human resources staff prevented him from getting a position.

Later, a friend mentioned Konami to him. Igarashi applied for an entry test at the multinational company, which he passed without problems. He focused on part-time work during his first year and, later, when he finished his studies, he began working full-time.

The first video game he participated in never saw the light of day —it was a simulation game developed by the company’s educational software department— but he had better luck with his next project, *Detana!! Twinbee*, an arcade game from 1991. This vertical-scrolling action game allowed up to two players —cooperative mode was included— to control Twinbee and Winbee, two machines piloted by human beings —designed by animator Shuzilow HA/Jujiro Hamakawa, who worked throughout the entire TwinBee saga— who faced hordes of alien enemies on the planet Meru.

Cover art of the PC Engine version of *Detana!! Twinbee*, alongside a screenshot of the game in the same version

This game already included in its team what would become Igarashi’s talismanic composer, Michiru Yamane —for *Detana!! Twinbee*, she worked alongside Hidenori Maezawa and Masae Nakashima—, whose work was already known from the *Ganbare Goemon* games. This composer would later leave Konami —before Igarashi and Hideo Kojima —to become a freelance composer in 2008.

Igarashi also worked on the second instalment of the spaceship shooter *Gradius*, *Gradius II* —also a scrolling action game, in this case a horizontal one— in 1992, as a programmer for its PC Engine version.

He also collaborated on the dating-sim game *Tokimeki Memorial*, released in 1994 for PC Engine, the same franchise in which Hideo Kojima had participated —coincidentally, another well-known name from the company, who left under circumstances never fully clarified. In this game, Igarashi was responsible for level design.

Igarashi's Arrival at Castlevania: The Immortal *Symphony of the Night*

Kōji was not interested in returning to work on a second instalment of the *Tokimeki Memorial* series, as he felt he did not have ideas that could be used as effectively as for other games. He thus requested Konami to move him to other projects, and the company finally agreed.

Castlevania would be the next franchise in which he participated. His first title would be, for many, his favourite *Castlevania*: the renowned *Castlevania: Symphony of the Night*—released in 1997 for PlayStation—. This game is considered a cult classic, as well as one of the greatest video games of all time, and also an unexpected success—a sleeper hit—, a game that is still played today—the author himself had spent several hours on it again while I was preparing this article.

Upon joining Konami, Igarashi was clear about what defined *Castlevania*: “a ‘macho’-looking hero energetically facing hordes of enemies,” and a game series that, being developed by different teams within Konami, lacked cohesion. Kōji decided that this had to change.

Original cover of the Japanese PlayStation version, designed by Ayami Kojima, and on the right, a screenshot from the English version

Although the director of *Symphony of the Night* was Toru Hagihara—who also served as producer and programmer on the game—he held Igarashi's work in high regard, with Igarashi acting as assistant director.

Symphony of the Night borrowed elements from Gunpei Yokoi's *Metroid* series and Shigeru Miyamoto's *The Legend of Zelda*. From *Metroid*—these types of games are referred to as “Metroidvania” within certain sectors of the gaming world—Igarashi incorporated aspects such as a vast interconnected map that the player would often need to traverse completely. Certain actions or items, such as speaking to a specific character or defeating (or not defeating) a level boss, would directly influence the player's progress.

Symphony of the Night offered numerous secrets—weapons, various items, and spells usable by the protagonist—and in fact hid nearly half of the entire game from the player.

This occurred through fulfilling, or failing to fulfil, certain conditions. For instance, the player could refrain from defeating the final enemy—who would later be revealed to be under control—thus opening a new possibility: exploring Dracula’s inverted castle. This was not simply a matter of flipping all the levels upside down and mirroring them; it introduced greater difficulty, new enemies, additional items and secrets, and the game’s true ending, which could only be experienced after ultimately defeating the real antagonist—Dracula.

This mechanic would become a hallmark of the games in which Kōji Igarashi was involved: so-called “good endings” and “bad endings.” If the player failed to discover the secrets that triggered the “good ending,” they would merely finish the game without experiencing the full story. It was a clever way to encourage players to explore every hidden nook and cranny of the adventure, making it far less repetitive or less motivating than other games of the era or even some more recent titles.

From *The Legend of Zelda* and other role-playing and adventure games, Igarashi borrowed elements such as character progression through experience levels—also increasing their statistics—and the use of items, equipment, and weapons that offered the player a variety of possibilities. As in *Metroid* and *The Legend of Zelda*, certain relics or pieces of equipment were required to advance through new areas, unlock sections, or activate the “good ending.” Depending on the item equipped, the player could perform different spells, while other items simply provided new attack or defence options.

This approach had not been seen since *Castlevania II: Simon’s Quest* (1987, Nintendo Entertainment System), albeit implemented in a different manner.

Left: Alucard casting a spell. Right: Alucard confronting Richter Belmont after facing him. In the “good ending,” he does not defeat Richter, and the battle pauses so that Alucard can assist Richter in confronting the true antagonist of the adventure.

All of the above was complemented by one of the finest examples of excellent sprite work ever seen in video games to date—Igarashi himself still praises the animator responsible—and a completely sublime soundtrack, composed by Michiru Yamane, whose pieces invite us to venture into Dracula’s castle.

Igarashi decided that Castlevania could feature a male protagonist, but with a completely different appearance from the classic Belmonts —strong, muscular, very masculine men. He wanted a hero who was elegant, more androgynous yet tragic in appearance, and with abilities very different from those previously known —until then, the Belmonts wielded weapons such as the Vampire Killer whip, along with various utility items that could also serve as thrown weapons like knives or axes.

Part of the credit for this aesthetic shift achieved in *Symphony of the Night* goes to a new addition: this evolution would not have been possible without understanding the vision of the artist Ayami Kojima, who helped give the Castlevania saga a visual identity entirely distinct from what had been known before.

The illustrator and painter imbued Castlevania and everything surrounding it with a baroque yet gothic style, simultaneously sweet and graceful, blending light and shadow in a way never seen before in a video game. Among other works —character designs, even a comic related to the game— Kojima created the cover shown earlier in this article.

You can watch and listen to Igarashi himself reminiscing about this video game classic (and playing it) alongside some interviewers by following this link. The interview is not to be missed.

Here are some samples of Ayami Kojima's work. Left: images from the *Symphony of the Night* manga, as they appear in the game's art book. Right: sketches showing the design of Dracula for *Symphony of the Night*.

Igarashi's role in the franchise gradually grew in importance, to the point that Kōji went from being just another member of the team to becoming, for years, the creative mind behind the franchise and the person responsible for establishing its official chronology.

Symphony of the Night also received a version for the Sega Saturn, which included additional content such as new levels and the possibility of controlling Maria Renard. It also updated Richter Belmont's sprites to resemble Ayami Kojima's artwork more closely, since the Richter in the original *Symphony* was exactly the same as in *Rondo of Blood*—the game chronologically preceding it, released in 1993 for the PC Engine.

After *Symphony of the Night*, Igarashi worked on the PlayStation game *Elder Gate*, published in 2000; a role-playing game in the pure JRPG style—that is, “Japanese Role-Playing Game”—with elements similar, in certain aspects, to the Final Fantasy or Dragon Quest series.

However, the former programmer could not completely detach himself from the Castlevania franchise—during his absence, the two Castlevania games for the Nintendo 64 were released.

In 2000, Igarashi participated in the PlayStation version of *Castlevania Chronicles*, a remake of one of the classic arcade-style games in the series, featuring the legendary vampire hunter Simon Belmont—the hero of the franchise's first entry in 1986, and also the second, 1987's *Simon's Quest*.

Igarashi's success with the portable Castlevania games

Following this, Igarashi entered what would become the golden age of Castlevania on handheld consoles. While Nintendo had released the notable *Castlevania: Circle of the Moon* in 2001, Igarashi felt that he should return to the series and contributed two titles to the Game Boy Advance, the platform on which that game appeared.

It is unclear whether it was due to not participating in the game himself or a matter of pride, but Igarashi has always been somewhat critical of *Circle of the Moon*, leaving it out of the official Castlevania timeline—although he appreciates the game, he critiques elements such as its control system and graphics. He would do the same with other titles in which he did not participate, such as *Castlevania Legends* (1997) for Game Boy, the last title to tell the adventures of the Belmonts on that handheld console.

Thus, in 2002, *Harmony of Dissonance* was released, an excellent game in which Igarashi participated as producer, level designer, and writer. It combined the already familiar “Metroidvania” elements with more classic features—the protagonist was a member of the Belmont clan, using the Vampire Killer whip as his weapon.

Harmony of Dissonance was well received, and IGA's team got to work again. They delivered *Castlevania: Aria of Sorrow* in 2003, also a success—although not as much in Japan as overseas, where it gained a stronger following—and became one of the most beloved Castlevania titles among fans of the series. It introduced features such as a skill system based on the protagonist, Soma Cruz, absorbing the souls of defeated enemies.

One of the aspects in which it stood out was its original soundtrack. *Harmony of Dissonance* had been criticised for its weak music —by Michiru Yamane— compared to what fans expected from Castlevania, so Igarashi once again collaborated with Yamane for *Aria of Sorrow*, resulting in an impeccable soundtrack, similar to *Dissonance* but following different directives given to the composer.

The team behind *Circle of the Moon* had not worked with Ayami Kojima, but Kōji Igarashi wanted her for his two Game Boy Advance titles. He developed both games almost simultaneously, intending to showcase “two distinct styles” of Castlevania. Playing with this duality, Kojima presented designs with medieval clothing —more familiar to *Castlevania* fans— for *Harmony of Dissonance*, and a contemporary style for *Aria of Sorrow* —which is set in the year 2035.

Promotional artwork for *Castlevania: Harmony of Dissonance* and *Castlevania: Aria of Sorrow*, created by Ayami Kojima

The so-called “Team IGA” —Kōji Igarashi’s development team— produced three more portable Castlevania games, this time for Nintendo DS. The first was *Castlevania: Dawn of Sorrow* (2005), the direct narrative sequel to *Aria of Sorrow*, in which players controlled Soma Cruz once again.

In 2006, Konami released *Castlevania: Portrait of Ruin*. On this occasion, players could control two protagonists, either separately or simultaneously. These were Jonathan Morris —a descendant of John Morris from *Castlevania Bloodlines* for the Sega Mega Drive/Genesis (1994), a game on which Yamane worked, featuring well-known pieces such as this one— and Charlotte Aulin —a powerful sorceress who perfectly complemented Jonathan’s close-range attacks and ranged weapons—. For this game’s soundtrack, Igarashi also enlisted the participation of Yūzō Koshiro.

Progressing through the story required interaction between the two characters, Jonathan and Charlotte, who could also perform truly devastating combined attacks against their enemies.

Igarashi's final portable Castlevania title was *Castlevania: Order of Ecclesia*, released in 2008—as mentioned earlier, also for the Nintendo DS—. Players took on the role of the mage Shanoa, who introduced the ability to summon both different weapons and a variety of spells, allowing players to adopt strategies highly adaptable to each situation.

The game incorporated classic elements of the series, such as entirely arcade-style levels in which the player simply advanced through the stage while defeating enemies, alongside aspects more closely associated with *Symphony of the Night*—an extensive map, the possibility of revisiting areas, the discovery of numerous secrets, and so on—.

Igarashi also produced the mobile phone game *Castlevania: Order of Shadows*, released in 2007. It featured very classic gameplay and included options such as replacing its soundtrack with that of other Castlevania titles. The Japanese producer was also behind *Castlevania: The Dracula X Chronicles* for the PlayStation Portable in 2007.

This game was a remake of the original *Castlevania: Rondo of Blood* for PC Engine (1993)—directed by Hagihara, who also worked on *Symphony of the Night*— and starred Richter Belmont and Maria Renard—protagonists alongside Alucard in *Symphony of the Night*. The same UMD disc also allowed players to play the original PC Engine version and *Castlevania: Symphony of the Night*. The artwork for this game was once again created by Kojima, while Michiru Yamane was responsible for producing the updated version of the original game's soundtrack.

Left: the original *Castlevania: Rondo of Blood* for PC Engine. Right: a screenshot from its remake, *Castlevania: The Dracula X Chronicles*.

Castlevania on home consoles and Igarashi's later work

Kōji Igarashi's influence over the franchise eventually became considerable. With the intention of presenting his own interpretation of the origins of the Belmont clan, he became involved in the development of *Castlevania: Lament of Innocence* for PlayStation 2 in 2003, in which the first Belmont in the saga's timeline appeared: Leon Belmont.

The game also recounts the tragedy of his family and the terrible fate of confronting Dracula. It further explores the origin of Dracula himself within the Castlevania saga through the characters Walter Bernhard and Mathias Cronqvist. Mathias would inherit Bernhard's legacy, as well as part of his ambition and powers, eventually becoming the future Dracula known to all followers of Castlevania.

In this title —and in the one that followed— the developers opted to present the adventure in three dimensions, rather than the classic two-dimensional format to which Castlevania had accustomed players —setting aside the two Nintendo 64 instalments—.

It was followed by *Castlevania: Curse of Darkness* in 2005, a game in which both Yamane and Kojima once again worked alongside Igarashi, as they had done on *Lament of Innocence*. In *Curse of Darkness*, players control Hector, a former servant of Dracula, and are also given the option to play as Trevor Belmont after completing the main adventure —one of the Belmont protagonists from the earlier, pre-Igarashi titles, who serves as an antagonist for part of this game.

The game introduced a more complex combat system than *Lament of Innocence*, allowing the player, once again —and unlike in the previous title, where whip-type weapons were used— a wider variety of methods for defeating enemies.

Left: Leon Belmont, protagonist of *Castlevania: Lament of Innocence*.
Right: Hector and Rosaly, characters from *Castlevania: Curse of Darkness*.

Igarashi was also responsible for producing less notable titles, such as the infamous *Castlevania: Judgement* (2008), a fighting game for Nintendo's Wii console. Aside from offering rather poor controls —partly due to the forced and awkward use of the Wii's motion controls in this case— and a largely dispensable story, the game also altered the design of some of the franchise's most iconic protagonists to the point of making them almost unrecognisable. These redesigns were created by Takeshi Obata, the artist behind *Death Note*. That said, the attempt to introduce a visual breath of fresh air was appreciated in certain cases.

In 2009, Igarashi produced the remake of the original *Castlevania: The Adventure* (1989) for the Game Boy, which was released through the Wii's online store, the Wii Shop Channel. This new version incorporated updated graphics and a higher-quality soundtrack —featuring arrangements of classic themes from across the series, including those from the Mega Drive titles. You can see the game in motion [here](#).

A year later, he was behind *Castlevania: Harmony of Despair*, released through the online stores of Xbox 360 and later PlayStation 3. This title is a crossover game —that is, one that combines different worlds and characters from various games— paying homage to some of the most emblematic titles and characters in the Castlevania franchise.

That same year, 2010, Konami released the first “major” *Castlevania* title in which Igarashi’s team was not involved, entrusting development instead to the Spanish studio MercurySteam. As much as it may hurt fans of Igarashi, they did a magnificent job with *Castlevania: Lords of Shadow*, which was released for Xbox 360, PlayStation 3, and PC—honestly, it is one of my favourite *Castlevania* games.

Harmony of Despair introduced a cooperative gameplay mode and the possibility of zooming the camera out to view larger portions of the stage, with the game remaining fully playable in this perspective. Once again, Kojima returned to collaborate with IGA on this project, although Michiru Yamane did not—the composition duties were instead handled by Yasuhiro Ichihashi and Tomoaki Hirono.

Charlotte Aulin and Jonathan Morris, from *Castlevania: Portrait of Ruin*, face a horde of enemies in *Castlevania: Harmony of Despair*

Kōji Igarashi was also behind *Otomedius Excellent*, released for Xbox 360 in 2011, a sequel to *Otomedius G (Gorgeous!)* (2008), a side-scrolling action game and spin-off of the *Gradius* franchise—in which Igarashi himself had previously worked, as mentioned earlier. It was not a particularly remarkable title, aside from the very appealing character designs aimed at audiences particularly fond of fan service.

Unfortunately, his final project at Konami was not especially notable either. It was the puzzle game *Leedmees* (2011), available for Xbox 360 via Xbox Arcade—the console’s online store—. Nevertheless, the idea of using one’s own body to solve puzzles with the help of Microsoft’s Kinect device was quite original.

Kōji Igarashi left Konami in 2014. The company would continue producing Castlevania games, but only *Lords of Shadow 2* for PlayStation 3, Xbox 360, and PC, and *Lords of Shadow: Mirror of Fate* for Nintendo 3DS were released afterwards —both very good titles. This did not prevent Konami from eventually shifting the franchise towards its pachinko machine business, even producing erotic-themed Castlevania games for those machines. After a period in which Igarashi gave no news about his projects, he suddenly reappeared with one of his own.

The project was titled *Bloodstained: Ritual of the Night*, and it was clearly intended to be the true successor to the classic Castlevania titles associated with Kōji Igarashi. When the Kickstarter campaign —a form of crowdfunding in which projects are financed by voluntary contributions from investors or fans, without the specific need for support from a company or bank— was launched in May 2015, Igarashi managed to raise even more money than initially requested within just two hours to fund the development of the game. At the time of writing the original version of this article, published on 31 August 2016, he was still working on the project alongside his team.

Some years ago, Igarashi faced a degree of controversy after stating that strong female warrior characters did not quite fit within the Castlevania universe —the fact that *Castlevania Legends*, whose protagonist was Sonia Belmont, had been removed from the official timeline did not help matters. After clarifying his comments later on, he introduced a character such as Shanoa, and now once again presented a determined female protagonist through Miriam in *Bloodstained*.

Igarashi initially requested five hundred thousand US dollars to finance the project, and in total the game raised more than five million five hundred thousand US dollars for its development and release. This gives a clear idea of how eagerly fans of Igarashi and of the classic Castlevania series were awaiting his work on this project.

Bloodstained: Ritual of the Night was originally scheduled for release in March 2017 on PC, Linux, Mac OS X, PlayStation 4, PlayStation Vita, Wii U, and Xbox One. Unfortunately, Igarashi decided that the game required more development time and postponed its release until 2018. Later, it had to be delayed once again by another year, which worried some enthusiasts who feared that the game might never see the light of day.

At the time when this article was originally published, Igarashi's team was working hard, hoping that the extra development time would allow the game to reach the highest possible level of quality and become a complete success. Fortunately, that is exactly what happened: *Bloodstained* was released on 18 June for Windows, PlayStation 4, and Xbox One, and on 25 June of the same year for Nintendo Switch —rather than Wii U—. The game proved to be a great success and a highly regarded title among Castlevania enthusiasts, although its sales were not extraordinary, reaching around two million units sold.

You can follow the evolution of the project on the official website and on the official *Bloodstained* YouTube channel, where Igarashi himself speaks about the development of the game.

Promotional *Bloodstained: Ritual of the Night* art by Yuji Natsume

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** Kickstarter, Castlevania Wiki, Gradius Wiki, 3DJuegos, Start, Shmuplations, The Jimquisition, Gamasutra, Konami | **Text written by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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